

MODELLING OF MULTI FUEL SUPPLY CHAINS

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1 SUMMARY

A novel multi-fuel energy generation system based on solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) technology could contribute significantly to the vision of a cleaner, sustainable maritime industry. To analyse different fuel pathways, the FuelSOME project develops a modular, open-source Python tool, the “Multi Fuel Pathway Explorer,” demonstrated in a real-world case study at the Port of Rotterdam (NL). Key findings include Methanol production by biomass gasification proving to be particularly promising due to its lower cost and high efficiency, while Ammonia scenarios using ion exchange technologies from wastewater demonstrated potential due to the overall high pathway efficiency but were cost-dominated by the exchange process and wastewater N-concentration. The results overall highlight the critical role of component-level modelling and fuel pathway configuration in optimizing performance and identifying system bottlenecks.

Keywords: sustainable fuels, energy efficiency for maritime applications, fuel cells, hydrogen, methanol, ammonia

2 ABSTRACT

Driven by stricter climate targets, the maritime sector must reduce greenhouse gas emissions and adopt cleaner energy systems. For deep-sea shipping, this requires technologies that are both scalable and robust while complying with regulatory standards. A promising approach is the integration of solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) with renewable fuels such as Hydrogen, Ammonia, or Methanol. Yet, the success of this solution depends on reliable supply chains that can consistently deliver the necessary fuel quality and volumes to ports across Europe. Preceding research in the FuelSOME project emphasizes the need of a structural and modular approach for setting up fuel pathways as a whole and the critical role of supply infrastructure in supporting fuel flexibility and reducing the overall environmental footprint of shipping operations, which provides the basis for the development of the Multi Fuel Pathway Explorer (MFPE).

The MFPE is a modular, open-source and Python-based simulation tool for modelling, simulating, and designing multi-fuel supply chains with a specific attention to capturing all key elements of the supply: starting from fuel production to transport and storage quantitative metrics like levelized cost of fuel (LCOF) and well-to-wake (W2W) efficiency are implemented to evaluate and compare the possible pathway variations. These variations can be examined in more detail with the scenario analysis functionality and the time-dependent simulation with a 1-hour time resolution can provide important information for supply pathway design planning. Emphasis is placed on the reusability, expandability and computational efficiency of the MFPE. Continuous improvement through additional modules is intended and the necessary foundation has been laid in the simulation setup. The MFPE implements a graph data structure to represent the fuel production pathways, which provides the necessary flexibility in the pathway design. Topological sorting enables a stage-wise analysis of flow behavior, propagating information through the graph. In the simulation in each time-step the entire graph is processed. This transient simulation allows the Multi Fuel Pathway Explorer to capture dynamic interactions between components within the fuel pathway. For the evaluation of the pathway the following key performance indicators are used: Levelized Cost of Fuel (LCOF) for economic evaluation; Pathway Efficiency (on a component-level and in a well-to-wake scope) to gain understanding for overall energy performance and identify opportunities to reduce energy losses throughout the pathway and finally Pathway Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is calculated as a pathway

average, a minimum TRL and a cost weighted pathway average to assess technical maturity and for development, and implementation strategies.

The MFPE library offers a collection of building blocks, called components, that can be freely combined in a plug-and-play manner to construct and simulate complete fuel pathways. Each component is created as a Python object and can be personalized during setup, for example by specifying its size, storage capacity, or energy supply mode. At the beginning of each simulation, a simulation time period is defined, after which the pathway is compiled and run. The component models in the Multi Fuel Pathway Explorer are designed to simulate the time-dependent behaviour of fuel flow, electricity demand, and losses within the pathway. Each component in the system is modelled to capture both its transient physical behaviour and the techno-economic characteristics necessary for system-level analysis. Each component handling fuel has an associated fuel type, which is checked for compatibility when connected to another component.

To illustrate the utilization of the MFPE the case study of the Port of Rotterdam (NL) is presented: In 2020, the Port of Rotterdam received 28,170 ocean-going vessels and 92,552 inland vessels, underlining its role as Europe's largest maritime hub; while exposed to transition risks such as stricter fuel policies and shifting markets, it also identifies opportunities in new cargo streams like hydrogen and renewable energy (Port of Rotterdam Authority, 2020/2024). At the same time, the Netherlands is developing hydrogen storage at Zuidwending with a planned capacity of about 26 million kg by 2030, alongside a national hydrogen backbone linking production, storage, and consumers to support maritime decarbonization (EES Europe, 2022; Zeeuw et al., 2023; Murray, 2022; JRC PVGIS, 2025).

Figure 1 shows the TRL and KPI summary for the use cases concerning the Port of Rotterdam. Looking at the bigger picture, current results show that Methanol provided by biomass gasification of wheat straw, pine forest and wood resulted in the lowest levelized costs of fuel with approx. 107-115 € per MWh respectively, followed by 169 € per MWh (Hydrogen by PEM) and 191 € per MWh (NH₃ by Haber Bosch) as well as 194 € per MWh (NH₃ by Ion Exchange from Industrial Wastewater). However, several other Use Cases and scenarios ranged between 220 and 340 € per MWh with an average of 280 +/- 44 € per MWh where differences were relatively small. However, ion exchange for NH₃ production also resulted in highest LCOF.

The W2W efficiency results from the MFPE simulations provide critical insights into the energy performance of different Hydrogen carrier fuel pathways across various Use Cases. These efficiencies reflect the ratio of useful energy delivered at the point of use relative to the primary energy input, encompassing conversion, transport, and storage losses along the entire pathway. Across all Use Cases, compressed Hydrogen consistently shows higher W2W efficiency compared to its liquefied counterpart, underlining the substantial energy penalty associated with liquefaction. In contrast, the Ammonia and Methanol fuel pathways generally exhibit better energy utilization. Especially Ammonia recovered from wastewater using Ion Exchange shows very high W2W efficiencies for scenarios where nitrogen concentrations are high in wastewater. Looking at the TRL of the individual components of the currently investigated Use Cases, the lowest (minimum) TRLs were found at 7 (system prototype and technology demonstrated). For the reference point of view (Year 2020) this is already demonstrating that most of the pre-defined technologies covered in the above stated Use Cases is quite mature.

The Multi Fuel Pathway Explorer (MFPE) has demonstrated its strength in simulating and analyzing complex, time-dependent fuel pathways with high technical fidelity. Despite the inherent system complexity and the uncertainties within and between parameters, the tool allows for comprehensive techno-economic and well-to-wheel (W2W) performance assessments across a range of Hydrogen carrier fuels and production scenarios. The high-resolution temporal modelling is particularly valuable for understanding dynamic behavior such as storage utilization, bottleneck formation, and the effect of intermittent energy supply (e.g., PV downtime), which are critical for real-world system design and scale-up. Overall, the MFPE tool provides a versatile and extensible simulation environment capable of informing system design, technology selection, and strategic planning. As

parameter databases improve and computational strategies evolve, MFPE will be even more effective in supporting the transition to a multi-carrier renewable fuel economy.

Figure 1: KPI summary comparison plot.

3 REFERENCES

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4 CONFERENCE TOPIC

Coupling of Energy Sectors, Life Cycle Assessment, Net-zero/negative Emissions in the Industry including CCUS

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